

THE ROLE OF TEACHING FOLKLORE IN DEVELOPING THE SPEECH OF PRIMARY GRADE STUDENTS

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Learning the native language is one of the most important steps for a child in early childhood. The first school years plays a critical role in owning the oral and linguistic competencies, since during this period they enrich their vocabulary, learn grammatical structures, and strengthen communicative skills. During this stage of development, well-selected learning materials can affect how quickly and effectively children learn to speak. The role of folklore, which includes fairy tales, proverbs, riddles, tongue twisters, folk songs, is especially invaluable, and it serves as an effective tool for the development of children's speaking skills. Unfortunately, in recent years, insensibility to the teaching the folk works in primary grades has increased, that is, students cannot correctly use simple proverbs in their speech, and because of that today they do not know why proverbs are necessary or do not understand their meaning. This indicates that we need to pay more attention to the teaching of folklore examples, which play an invaluable pedagogical role in improving children's speech skills, increasing their volume in school textbooks, as well as instilling in them that they occupy a large place in the culture of our nation

It should be noted that not all types of folklore works are taught in primary grades, but small-scale types corresponding to their age characteristics and not having a very complex linguistic structure are used. For example, fairy tales, riddles, tongue twisters, proverbs, legends, as well as excerpts from epics. Through small forms of folklore,

children develop sensitivity to language, learn to use various means, select the right words, and gradually master the figurative system of language.³⁴

A **fairy tale** (alternative names include fairytale, fairy story, household tale, magic tale, or wonder tale) is a short story that belongs to the folklore genre.³⁵ This example of oral folk art is one of the most widespread types in primary grades, and children begin to get acquainted with works of this genre from the 1st grade. Children love fairy tales because their content is very interesting and written in a language that is simple and understandable to children.

A **riddle** is a type of question that describes something in a difficult and confusing way and has a clever or funny answer, often asked as a game.³⁶ Riddles not only help sharpen students' brains but also help develop their language skills and communicative abilities. The reason is that in the process of giving a riddle to another classmate, students learn how to return the question and answer it, and also try to communicate freely with other children without embarrassment.

A **tongue twister** is a specially invented phrase with a difficult-to-pronounce combination of sounds, a quickly spoken humorous saying.³⁷ Despite the fact that tongue twisters are necessarily read quickly, they teach a child who is hurrying in speech pronounce phrases more slowly, not "eating" the endings, so that they can be understood.

A **proverb** is a folk saying that expresses not the opinion of individuals, but rather the nation's assessment, the nation's mind.³⁸ Through the use of proverbs, students learn to express each sentence briefly, concisely, and broadly in terms of meaning.

A **legend** is a genre of folklore that consists of a narrative featuring human actions, believed or perceived to have taken place in human history.³⁹ Through reading legends, students develop the ability to listen to others and develop connected speech.

³⁴ Власова Л.И. Методическая разработка «Развитие речи детей младшего школьного возраста посредством малых форм фольклора». 2022 год.

³⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fairy_tale

³⁶ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/riddle>

³⁷ Ожегова С. И, Шведова Н. Ю. «Толковый словарь русского языка». Изд. 4-е, доп. М., 1997. с.1817

³⁸ Слюсарева А.А. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ПОСЛОВИЦ И ПОГОВОРОК В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ.

³⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Legend>

Folklore works can be beneficial to improve young children’s speaking skills in many different ways:

1. **Firstly**, through reading and listening fairy tales or legends they learn new words in meaningful situations, which makes it easier for them to understand and remember those words. As N. Gavrish notes, "It is very important to accelerate the "birth" of the first conscious words in a child at an early age." Small forms of folklore, in which its attention is drawn to objects, animals, and people, will help increase the vocabulary.⁴⁰

2. **Secondly**, since the development of events in such folklore examples is very interesting and simple, children do not get bored reading them, which does not cause them much difficulty in establishing cause-and-effect relationships between the characters.

3. **Thirdly**, in many types of folklore, such as riddles, proverbs, and songs, simple rhymes are used, and sentences end with the same letter or word, which helps children remember them quickly and learn to pronounce letters correctly. About this, A. D Matskevich says: "Small forms of folklore are compact and precise in form, deep and rhythmic. With their help, children learn to pronounce sounds clearly and distinctly."⁴¹

For example:

At balasın tayınshaq deydi, A horse's child is called a foal,
Qoy balasın qozışhaq deydi, Sheep’s child is called a lamb,
Túye balasın botalaq deydi, Camel’s child is called a calf,
Túlki balasın ne deydi?!⁴² What is a fox’s baby called?!

Through this example of a tongue twister, the student learns the names of new animals, such as "horse," "foal," "sheep," "lamb," "camel," "calf," "fox," and also practices the correct pronunciation of these words.

4. **Fourthly**, folklore can help children to improve their storytelling abilities. By retelling folklore works, they learn how to organize their thoughts and convey them in

⁴⁰ Загруддинова М., Гавришин «Использование малых форм фольклора» Д/в – 1991г., № 9, с. 16 – 22.

⁴¹ Мацкевич А.Д. «Малые формы фольклора» (работа с книгой в д/с сост. В.А. Богуславская, В.Д. Разова) – М.: Просвещение.

⁴² Abdinazimov.Sh., Qutlimuratov. B, Ismaylova. Z, Saliyeva. P, Qutlimuratova.G. Ana tili hám oqıw sawatlılıǵı 1-bólim: 1klass ushın sabaqlıq /– Tashkent: Respublika bilimlendiriw orayı, 2021. – b. 55

a logical sequence, and also learns construct sentences grammatically correctly, for example, they can practice how to use words in person, number, and tense according to the sentence.

5. **Fifthly**, folklore can impact on their communicative skills in a positive way. For instance, in most of the folk songs dialogues are used which give students the chance to speak, listen to others and build confidence to speak up and share ideas.

6. **Finally**, children's folklore inspires children to improvise and think creatively. By inventing new words, melodies, or rhythms, children gain the opportunity to reveal their creative nature and express their individuality. This contributes to the development of their creative thinking and imagination, which is important for the development of the individual as a whole.⁴³

In conclusion, using folklore in primary school is an effective way to develop children's speech. Through its rich vocabulary, rhythmic language and clear storytelling patterns, folklore helps children build vocabulary, improve pronunciation and gain confidence. For these reasons, folklore should be included regularly in language teaching.

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6. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Legend>

⁴³ Маликова У. Б. ВЛИЯНИЕ ДЕТСКОГО ФОЛЬКЛОРА НА РАЗВИТИЕ РЕЧИ ДЕТЕЙ// Educational Research in Universal Sciences. VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 10-2023. с.133

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